

Synthesis of Some 3-Arylimino-5-(N-Methylanilino)-1,2,4- Δ^4 -Dithiazolines

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Some new 3-arylimino-5-(N-methylanilino)-1,2,4- Δ^4 -dithiazolines have been synthesised by the oxidative debenylation and cyclisation of the corresponding 5-aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets. The characterisation of these compounds have been achieved by the direct oxidation of the corresponding 2,4-dithiobiurets and also by infrared spectra.

OXIDATION of 2,4-dithiobiurets has been a well studied method¹⁻⁵ for the synthesis of the related 1,2,4-dithiazolines/dithiazolidines. In the recent past we reported that substituted 1,2,4-dithiazolines/dithiazolidines could also be synthesised by the oxidative dealkylation of the related isodithiobiurets⁶⁻¹⁰. In the light of these observations, it was considered of interest to explore the potentiality of oxidative debenylation and cyclisation reaction for the synthesis of certain hitherto unreported 3-arylimino-5-(N-methylanilino)-1,2,4- Δ^4 -dithiazolines.

The present communication describes the synthesis of certain new 3-arylimino-5-(N-methylanilino)-1,2,4- Δ^4 -dithiazolines by the oxidative debenylation and simultaneous ring closure of the corresponding 5-aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets.

N-Methylphenyl thiourea was benzylated with benzyl chloride. The expected 1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzylisothiourea free base (I) thus obtained was condensed with the appropriate arylisothiocyanate to yield the desired 5-aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets (II). These isodithiobiurets (II), on oxidation with molecular bromine in chloroform, gave the related 3-arylimino-5-(N-methylanilino)-1,2,4- Δ^4 -dithiazolines (IV). These have also been obtained by the direct oxidation of the related 5-aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2,4-dithiobiurets (III). Compounds (III) were obtained by the reductive debenylation of the corresponding isodithiobiurets (II) with dry hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine medium and also by the reduction of the related dithiazolines (IV) with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide.

In all the cases the structure of the compounds (III) and (IV) were confirmed by their synthesis through alternative route as described above and also by mixed melting point, elemental analysis and identical ir spectra. The scheme of the reaction can be represented as follows.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds are recorded on Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded in Nujol on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model-720. N-Methylphenyl thiourea was prepared according to known procedure¹¹ and its S-benzyl derivative (I) was obtained by benzylation¹² with benzyl chloride.

5-Aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets (II): The details of a typical experiment is as follows. The 1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzylisothiourea, m.p. 70° (5.0 g; 0.019 mole) was refluxed with *m*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate (3.21 g; 0.019 mole) in dry benzene for 4 hr on a water bath. The excess of benzene was evaporated and the semi-solid product, on washing with petroleum ether and treatment with a little ethanol, afforded 5-*m*-methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret as a crystalline product. It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 90°, yield 6.16 g (75%). The results of such experiments are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 5-ARYL-1,1-METHYLPHENYL-2-S-BENZYLISO-4-THIOBIURETS II (a-f)

Com-pound	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis%			
				Calcd.		Found	
				C	H	C	H
IIa	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS ₂	198	75	65.55	5.46	65.90	5.50
IIb	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	127	74	68.14	5.67	68.30	5.71
IIc	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS ₂	90	75	65.55	5.46	65.80	5.53
II d	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ S ₂	118	69	62.04	4.70	62.23	4.91
IIe	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	122	64	68.14	5.67	68.21	5.71
II f	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	88	50	68.14	5.67	68.20	5.73

Typical IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 5-*m*-methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret : 3200m NH stretching (lit. 3400-3100)¹³; 1125m, 1140vs, 1200w N-C(=S)-N grouping (lit. 1100-1200)^{14a}; 1600w N-C=N grouping (lit. 1685-1582)^{14a}.

3-Arylimino-5-(*N*-methylanilino)-1,2,4-Δ⁴-dithiazolines (IV) :

(i) *Oxidative debenylation of 5-aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets* : The experimental details of a typical experiment follows : The 5-*m*-methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret (2 g). made into a paste with chloroform, was treated with molecular bromine with vigorous stirring until the colour of bromine persisted. The reaction mixture warmed up appreciably evolving lachrymatory fumes of benzyl bromide. After 1 hr the semi-solid product was first washed with ether and the addition of a little ethanol thereafter gave the hydrobromide of the oxidation product which separated out as a crystalline product. On treatment with aqueous ammonia 3-*m*-methoxyphenylimino-5-(*N*-methylanilino)-1,2,4-Δ⁴-dithiazoline was obtained, which was thoroughly washed with ether and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 168°, yield 1.06 g (68%).

The dithiazoline bases so obtained showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with authentic samples obtained by the oxidation of the corresponding 1,1,5-trisubstituted-2,4-dithiobiurets (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 3-ARYLIMINO-5-(*N*-METHYLANILINO)-1,2,4-Δ⁴-DITHIAZOLINES IV (a-f)

Com-pound	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis%			
				Calcd.		Found	
				C	H	C	H
IVa	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS ₂	110	78	58.35	4.55	58.61	4.49
IVb	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂	94	71	61.34	4.79	61.54	4.83
IVc	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS ₂	168	68	58.35	4.55	58.63	4.56
IVd	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	85	70	53.97	3.59	54.02	3.71
IVe	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂	110	72	61.34	4.79	61.79	4.82
IVf	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂	125	60	61.34	4.79	61.80	4.79

Typical IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 3-*m*-methoxyphenylimino-5-(*N*-methylanilino)-1,2,4-Δ⁴-dithiazoline : C=N 1625¹⁵; ring S-S-linkage 488s¹⁵; the absence of IR band for N-H is remarkable.

(ii) *Oxidation of 5-aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2,4-dithiobiurets (III) with bromine in ethanol* : 5-*m*-Methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (2 g), listed in Table 3, was oxidised with bromine in ethanolic solution. The excess of ethanol was

evaporated and the resultant mass washed with ether when hydrobromide of the 3-*m*-methoxyphenylimino-5-(*N*-methylanilino)-1,2,4-Δ⁴-dithiazoline was obtained. The free base was obtained by the treatment of the hydrobromide with aqueous ammonia and it was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 168°, yield 1.5 (80%) (Table 2).

5-Aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2,4-dithiobiurets (III) :

(i) *Reductive debenylation of 5-aryl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets (II) with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine medium* : Through a solution of 5-*m*-methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret (5 g) in pyridine (50 ml) and triethylamine (6 ml), a stream of dry hydrogen sulphide was passed for 4 hr. The reddish brown viscous liquid so obtained was poured over crushed ice, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and diluted with water. On standing for about 1 hr, 5-*m*-methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret was obtained as a granular solid. Purification was effected by dissolving the product in dilute aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitation with hydrochloric acid followed by crystallisation from ethanol, m.p. 132°, yield 61% (Table 3).

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF 5-ARYL-1,1-METHYLPHENYL-2,4-DITHIOBIURETS III (a-f)

Com-pound	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis%			
				Calcd.		Found	
				C	H	C	H
IIIa	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	160	69	58.00	5.13	58.13	5.39
IIIb	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂	169	63	60.95	5.39	61.10	5.43
IIIc	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	132	61	58.00	5.13	58.29	5.17
III d	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	102	59	53.65	4.17	53.71	4.19
IIIe	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂	110	58	60.95	5.39	61.09	5.25
III f	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂	98	60	60.95	5.39	61.21	5.41

Typical IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 5-*m*-methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2,4-dithiobiurets : 3385w NH-stretching¹³; 1155m N-C(=S)-N - grouping^{14a}.

(ii) *Reduction of 3-arylimino-5-(N-methylanilino)-1,2,4-Δ⁴-dithiazolines with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide* : 3-*m*-Methoxyphenylimino-5-(*N*-methylanilino)-1,2,4-Δ⁴-dithiazolines (4 g) was dissolved in hot ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide solution and a stream of hydrogen sulphide passed for 3 hr. The clear solution thus obtained on dilution with water or acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid afforded 5-*m*-methoxyphenyl-1,1-methylphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 132° yield 61% (Table 3).

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